

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1. MapMan overview of DEGs related with stress-related genes and metabolism processes in *tef* under drought stress. (A) Overview of stress-related genes differentially regulated under drought stress (**Table S4**). (B) Overview of metabolism genes differentially regulated under drought conditions. Differentially expressed genes (fold change > 2, *p*-val < 0.05) are represented as red (down-regulated) and blue (up-regulated) squares. Values in the legend are log₂-transformed fold changes (**Table S5**).

Figure S2. MapMan overview of DEGs involved in signaling in *tef* under drought stress. Overview of protein kinases receptor differentially regulated under drought stress in *tef*. Values in the legend are log₂-transformed fold changes (**Table S6**).

Figure S3. Expression pattern of genes encoding members related to hormone signaling in *tef* under drought stress. (A) Brassionosteroids and (B) Auxins related genes. Differentially expressed genes (fold change > 2, p-val < 0.05) are represented as red (down-regulated) and blue (up-regulated) squares. The complete list of genes involved hormone signaling is in **Table S4**.

A

B

Figure S4. Distribution of TF families upregulated in tef (Tsedey) under drought stress. (A) Percentage of up-regulated TFs families under drought stress. (B) Heatmap of Z-scores showing the expression profile of the top 10 transcription factors up-regulated under drought. Differentially expressed genes (fold change > 2, p-val < 0.05) are represented as red (down-regulated) and blue (up-regulated). The complete list of genes is in **Table S7**.

A

B

Figure S5. Distribution of TF families downregulated in tef under drought stress. (A) Percentage of down-regulated TFs families under drought stress. (B) Heatmap of Z-scores showing the expression profile of the top 20 transcription factors down-regulated under drought. Differentially expressed genes (fold change > 2, p-val < 0.05) are represented as red (down-regulated) and blue (up-regulated). The complete list of genes is in Table S7.

Figure S6. Expression pattern of genes involved in abiotic stress according to MapMan analysis. Overview of abiotic stress-related genes differentially regulated in *tef* under drought stress. Differentially expressed genes (fold change > 2, p-val < 0.05) are represented as red (down-regulated) and blue (up-regulated) squares. The complete list of genes that are involved in abiotic stress is in **Table S4**.

Figure S7. Expression pattern of genes encoding member of inorganic antioxidant classes in tef under drought stress. Differentially expressed genes (fold change > 2, p-val < 0.05) are represented as red (down-regulated) and blue (up-regulated) squares. GRX: glutaredoxin, THRX: thioredoxin, PRX: Peroxidases, GR: Glutathione, Asc Ox: Ascorbate oxidase. The complete list of genes involved in antioxidant response is in **Table S4**.

A

C

Figure S9. Expression pattern of genes encoding members related to cell wall regulation and starch/sucrose metabolism in *tef* under drought stress. (A) Cell wall-related genes and (B) genes differentially expressed involved in starch/sucrose metabolism. Differentially expressed genes (fold change > 2, p-val < 0.05) are represented as red (down-regulated) and blue (up-regulated) squares. The complete list of genes is in **Table S5**. (C) Starch and cell wall metabolism biosynthesis pathways where the red and blue circles represent the genes that were upregulated and downregulated respectively in the RNA-Seq in *tef* under drought stress. Abbreviations: HXK: Hexokinase, Glc1P: glucose 1-phosphate, Glc6P: glucose 6-phosphate, AGPase: adenosine 5'-diphosphate glucose pyrophosphorylase, ADP-Glucose: adenosine diphosphate glucose, UGPase: UDP-glucose pyrophosphorylase, PGM: phosphoglucomutase, GBSS: granule bound starch synthase and UDP-Glucose: Uridine-5-diphosphate. UDP-Glucose is necessary for the synthesis of cellulose and pectins. T6P: Trehalose 6-phosphate, TPP: Trehalose 6-phosphate phosphatase, TPS: Trehalose-6-phosphate synthase. In the left corner a simplified representation of the cell wall structure.